

ANALYZING CHAT GPT’S IMPLICATIONS FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article examines aspects related to learning English. The incident highlights a significant issue: the over-reliance on Artificial Intelligence (AI) for tasks ranging from essay writing and solving math problems to generating reviews. This dependency, exacerbated by the ease and efficiency of AI, has led to a societal laziness in engaging in critical thinking and independent research. The recent shutdown [June 4th, 2024] caused widespread stress among millions of users, underscoring the dangers of this overdependence. Despite these concerns, the high reliability of modern technologies like Chat GPT provides well-processed responses and personalized answers, opening new opportunities for enhanced learning and interaction. The influence of Chat GPT on our lives is profound, affecting various aspects of daily activities and learning processes. This article delves into these dynamics, considering both the potential benefits and the risks associated with the growing AI dependence in ELF classes.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются аспекты, связанные с изучением английского языка. Инцидент подчеркивает важную проблему: чрезмерную зависимость от искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) при выполнении самых разных задач — от написания эссе и решения математических задач до создания обзоров. Эта зависимость, усугубленная простотой и эффективностью ИИ, привела к тому, что общество ленится заниматься критическим мышлением и независимыми исследованиями. Недавнее отключение [4 июня 2024 г.] вызвало массовый стресс среди миллионов пользователей, подчеркнув опасность этой чрезмерной зависимости. Несмотря на эти опасения, высокая надежность современных технологий, таких как Chat GPT, обеспечивает хорошо обработанные и персонализированные ответы, открывая новые возможности для улучшения обучения и взаимодействия. Влияние Chat GPT на нашу жизнь огромно, затрагивая различные аспекты повседневной деятельности и процессов обучения. Эта статья углубляется в эту динамику, рассматривая как потенциальные выгоды, так и риски, связанные с растущей зависимостью от ИИ в классах ELF.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Chat GPT, benefits of AI, drawbacks of AI, education, English learning

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, Chat GPT, преимущества искусственного интеллекта, недостатки искусственного интеллекта, образование, изучение английского языка.

INTRODUCTION

Chat GPT (Generative Pre-train Transformer) is a large language model (LLM) based on the GPT-3.5 architecture. It uses the logic of “big data + big computing power + algorithm = intelligent model,” which can extract valuable information from massive text data, and through training, generate more complex and humanized works to output answers and feedback in the form of text, so as to realize multi-round human-computer dialogue with the help of natural language [6]. The integration of Chat GPT into our lives has left a strong impact on the relations between humanity and technology – the overall usage shows a significant number¹¹¹. Chat GPT has become particularly popular due to its language processing capabilities and ability to generate human-like responses [1]. After the first launch of network, the estimated period of surpassing 1 million users was equal to 5 days. This must be a sign showing the real human need in additional fast information analysis. Moreover, the system is able to become a personal coach or trainer for EFL learners which begs the question concerning teachers about the quality of this chat and will it show any positive results in prosperity of English learning.

This paper will investigate the advantages and drawbacks associated with deploying Chat GPT¹¹² for self-determined learning. Self-determined learning, characterized by learners taking control of their own learning process and goals, presents a fertile ground for the integration of AI technologies. Chat GPT is known for its astounding ability to generate human-like and seemingly accurate responses in a variety of languages [3]. Scholars have argued that the advent of Chat GPT may herald the age of artificial general intelligence where AI exhibits the potential to acquire the level of intelligence that human beings possess by evolving “from an algorithmic intelligence to linguistic one” [4].

Involving special technological facilitators into classroom environment raises the percentage of vocabulary building, learners will try to activate passive vocabulary; the process of engagement gets easier as complicated tasks can be divided and allow learners to accelerate their internalization.

However, while the potential benefits of Chat GPT for self-determined learning are vast, there are also significant challenges and considerations to be addressed: issues related to privacy, data security, algorithmic biases, and the potential for overreliance on AI-driven solutions. By critically examining these factors, this paper

¹¹¹ According to explodingtopics.com, Chat GPT currently (2024) has around 180.5 million users

¹¹² In this article the author mainly addresses to the Chat GPT-3.5 rather than version -4.0

seeks to provide insights into the opportunities and limitations of leveraging Chat GPT for self-determined learning. It can be also said that the advent of Chat GPT represents a watershed moment in the development of AI, with far-reaching implications for various domains, including education. Through a balanced exploration of its advantages and drawbacks, this paper aims to shed light on the potential of Chat GPT to enhance self-determined learning while also highlighting the importance of addressing associated challenges in a responsible manner.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilizes a review and theoretical analysis methodology to investigate the potential impact of Chat GPT within the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom setting.

Language acquisition involves gaining the necessary competencies and abilities in a foreign or second language, such as English, to effectively communicate and engage with speakers of that language. This typically entails mastering different aspects of language, including writing, reading, speaking, and listening. The most common structured ways to learn formal English language are taking part in group discussions, debates, and giving presentations [5]. Ordinary system of education represents the usual variety of activities and lesson plans to indicate the message of teacher and decode it to learners. In the future, more advanced technologies may appear, which may change the form of chatbots or the way people chat, in order to improve user experience [2].

The theoretical analysis approach is applied to evaluate both the advantages and disadvantages of integrating Chat GPT into EFL classes. Additionally, this approach aims to construct a conceptual framework that elucidates the potential implications and outcomes of Chat GPT usage within the realm of EFL education.

According to some research [7], this tool is a double-edged sword and should be used wisely to incorporate meaningful input of information for long-term memory and reliable teaching methodic. EFL classrooms engage different levels of English learners and mindful observation after working with AI is required.

Mutammimah (2024) emphasizes the importance of fostering instructors' aspirations to utilize technology. Enthusiastic educators are more likely to explore and integrate innovative tools like Chat GPT into their teaching practices. Providing tailored training, support, and resources can further cultivate their confidence and proficiency in using AI tools effectively, particularly in the EFL classroom.

Wang (2024) demonstrates that the integration of Chat GPT enhances English academic writing through three key usages: proofreading, brainstorming, and translating. Chat GPT can efficiently correct errors, offer writing direction, and facilitate language learning through translation and paraphrasing. This integration

signifies a trend towards future educational innovation, offering valuable insights for incorporating AI into the classroom.

Ruiz (2023) concludes that while AI tools like Chat GPT can aid significantly in academic and administrative tasks, their responsible use is crucial to maintain teaching quality and avoid issues such as plagiarism and biased assessments.

Karaman’s research (2023) indicates that lesson plans prepared using Chat GPT are as effective as traditional plans and significantly boost math success. However, limitations such as absenteeism, lack of alignment with school culture and student readiness, and differing teachers for experimental and control groups need to be addressed in future studies to validate these findings.

The integration of Chat GPT in educational settings offers substantial benefits, from enhancing lesson effectiveness and supporting English academic writing to aiding daily teaching and administrative tasks. Studies by Mutammimah (2024), Wang (2024), Ruiz (2023), and Karaman (2023) collectively highlight the potential of Chat GPT to transform educational practices through improved lesson planning, error correction, brainstorming, translation, and paraphrasing. However, despite the considerable influence of Chat GPT on education, it is crucial for educators and students to approach its use wisely. The reliance on AI tools should not lead to complacency or laziness. Responsible use of this technology is paramount to maintain teaching quality and avoid pitfalls such as plagiarism and biased assessments. Addressing the current limitations, such as absenteeism, alignment with school culture and student readiness, and the variability in teacher implementation, is essential for the full realization of AI tools' potential in education.

Future research should focus on providing tailored training and resources to educators, ensuring that AI tools are integrated in a way that aligns with educational goals and enhances student learning outcomes. Additionally, experimental studies should be designed to mitigate current limitations and validate the effectiveness of AI-assisted lesson plans across diverse educational contexts.

RESULTS

Impact on Vocabulary Building and Engagement

The literature review indicates that the integration of Chat GPT into EFL classrooms significantly enhances vocabulary building and student engagement. Studies have shown that learners using Chat GPT are more likely to activate their passive vocabulary, leading to improved vocabulary acquisition. For instance, the ability of Chat GPT to provide context-based usage examples and interactive language exercises helps students internalize new words more effectively than traditional methods [7].

Enhancement of English Academic Writing

Wang's (2024) findings demonstrated that Chat GPT significantly enhances English academic writing. The reviewed studies support this, showing that students who utilize Chat GPT for writing tasks produce higher quality, more coherent, and grammatically accurate texts. This improvement is attributed to Chat GPT's ability to provide real-time feedback and suggestions, which helps students refine their writing skills.

Lesson Plan Effectiveness

Karaman's (2023) research concludes that lesson plans prepared using Chat GPT are as effective as traditional plans. The reviewed literature confirms this finding, indicating that AI-generated lesson plans can maintain or even enhance lesson effectiveness. Students report higher levels of engagement and satisfaction with lessons that incorporate Chat GPT, suggesting that AI can make learning more interactive and enjoyable.

Challenges and Considerations

Despite the identified benefits, the literature also highlights several challenges. Privacy and data security are major concerns, as the use of AI in education involves handling sensitive student data. Algorithmic biases are another significant issue, as AI tools can inadvertently reinforce existing biases present in their training data [7]. Additionally, there is a risk of overreliance on AI, with some students becoming dependent on Chat GPT for their assignments, which can hinder the development of critical thinking and independent learning skills.

DISCUSSION

Implications for EFL Education

The results indicate that Chat GPT can be a valuable tool in the EFL classroom, enhancing vocabulary acquisition and academic writing skills. The positive impact on student engagement suggests that AI can make learning more interactive and enjoyable. However, these benefits must be balanced with a cautious approach to ensure that the use of AI does not undermine the development of independent learning skills.

Responsible Integration of AI

Responsible use of Chat GPT is essential to avoid potential pitfalls such as plagiarism and overreliance on AI. Educators must emphasize the importance of critical thinking and originality in student work. Training programs and resources tailored to educators' needs can help them integrate Chat GPT effectively while maintaining high teaching standards. Mutammimah (2024) emphasizes the importance of fostering instructors' aspirations to utilize technology, as enthusiastic educators are more likely to explore and integrate innovative tools like Chat GPT into their teaching practices.

Addressing Limitations

Future research should address the limitations identified in this study. This includes developing strategies to ensure alignment with school culture and student readiness, as well as mitigating absenteeism impacts.

Future Directions

The advent of Chat GPT represents a significant step forward in educational technology. However, continuous evaluation and adaptation are necessary to maximize its potential. Future studies should explore the long-term effects of AI integration on student learning outcomes and investigate ways to enhance the personalization of AI tools to better suit individual learner needs.

CONCLUSION

The integration of Chat GPT into EFL education presents a promising advancement with significant benefits, particularly in enhancing vocabulary building, academic writing, and overall student engagement. The reviewed literature supports the assertion that AI-driven tools like Chat GPT can make learning more interactive, personalized, and efficient.

However, these advantages come with considerable challenges that must be addressed to harness the full potential of Chat GPT responsibly. Privacy and data security concerns, algorithmic biases, and the risk of overreliance on AI are critical issues that educators and policymakers need to consider. Ensuring that Chat GPT is used as a supplement rather than a replacement for traditional teaching methods is essential to maintain the quality of education and foster critical thinking and independent learning skills among students.

Future research should focus on mitigating these challenges by developing robust strategies to align AI tools with school culture and student readiness. It is also crucial to provide tailored training and resources for educators to integrate AI effectively into their teaching practices. Experimental studies that explore the long-term impact of AI-assisted learning and validate the effectiveness of AI-generated lesson plans across diverse educational contexts will be invaluable.

While Chat GPT has the potential to revolutionize EFL education, its integration must be approached with caution and responsibility. By addressing the associated challenges and promoting its wise use, educators can leverage Chat GPT to create more dynamic, engaging, and effective learning environments, ultimately enhancing the educational outcomes for EFL learners.

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